

Big Bang, graviton film and quark-gluon plasma

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Abstract

To demonstrate the proposed model of the quark-gluon plasma as a quark-gluon gas confined within a graviton film, two conditions must be met: 1) the pressure of the quark-gluon gas should not break the bond of the graviton film, and 2) the gas must not leak outside the film. We proved both conditions. First, we showed that the quark-gluon gas pressure does not exceed the potential energy density of the graviton film since its formation in the early universe. Although the strong interaction allows for the possibility of the gas leaking via hadronization, we ruled out this scenario by demonstrating that hadrons produced outside the graviton film immediately fall toward the film due to its gravitational potential energy. This gravitational potential arises from the nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect of real gravitons composing the film, which acquire an effective mass on the Planck scale, as shown in previous literature. Therefore, we provided a complete proof that the confined quark-gluon gas cannot escape the graviton film.

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1 Introduction

Graviton instability was shown in [1] at the quantum field theoretic level, and it was also demonstrated there that gravitons may possibly form a film structure. The binding energy of gravitons per pair is extremely large, on the order of the Planck energy, E_P [1]; therefore, this bond between two gravitons cannot be easily broken. The possibility that this graviton film confines a quark-gluon gas ¹, serving as the true description of the quark-gluon plasma (QGP), was proposed in [3]. Based on these discussions, the possibility that a graviton film surrounding the nucleus exists in every atom was suggested in [1].

Within three minutes after the Big Bang [4, 5], it is believed that there was a sudden change in temperature, and Big Bang nucleosynthesis took place after the QGP era. Tracing back to the Big Bang, was there ever a moment when the energy density of the graviton film balanced the pressure of the quark-gluon gas it confines? This is a natural question to ask. Not only is it natural, but it is also an essential question for confirming whether the structure of a graviton film confining a quark-gluon gas is robust. One must confirm that no such moment existed—except at the very moment of the graviton film’s formation—since the graviton film has persisted, along with quarks and gluons, up to the present moment.

Confirming that such a balance never occurs, and that the graviton film is bound more strongly than the pressure of the quark-gluon gas (except at the moment of its formation in the early universe), demonstrates that the graviton film confining a gas of quarks and gluons can robustly exist from its formation in the early universe—where we view it as the quark-gluon plasma—up to the present moment.

This structure may be viewed as the “seed of the atomic nucleus” that formed in the early universe. As the universe evolved and its temperature decreased, this structure eventually gave rise to the atomic nucleus.

¹The state of quarks and gluons released from hadrons was discussed in [2].

In the early universe, before $t = 10^{-6}$ seconds after the Big Bang, the background temperature is estimated to have been extremely high—too high for hadronization to occur. In such a scenario, since hadronization does not take place, demonstrating that the pressure of the quark-gluon gas confined within the graviton film is smaller than the energy density of the graviton film suffices to prove that the gas cannot escape from the film, and thus remains confined within it.

However, in the early universe at $t = 10^{-6}$ seconds after the Big Bang, or at later times, the background temperature would have cooled sufficiently to allow hadronization. In this situation, if the quark-gluon gas were to escape from the graviton film, it would undergo a phase transition from a high-energy to a low-energy state, since the gas itself exists in a high-energy state, whereas the space outside the graviton film is in a low-energy state. This phase transition must occur at the film when the gas attempts to escape. Due to the nature of the strong interaction, the interaction between the escaping portion of the gas and the rest of the gas becomes extremely strong, preventing the gas from escaping. Thus, the impossibility of the entire gas escaping is demonstrated by showing that the pressure of the quark-gluon gas confined within the graviton film is smaller than the energy density of the graviton film.

Still, there is one unique possibility for the quark-gluon gas to leak outside the graviton film: hadronization [6]. The quark-gluon gas, attempting to escape could theoretically produce a hadron just outside the film (very close to its boundary) and emit it as radiation. This is the only remaining possibility—but as we will demonstrate, it does not occur.

As argued in [1], real gravitons constituting the graviton film acquire an effective mass on the order of the Planck mass, m_P . Owing to the strong attractive gravitational potential generated by the graviton film, any hadron produced outside the film would immediately fall back toward it and would be unable to escape its gravitational pull.

There are two main themes in this paper:

1. Investigating whether there was a moment after the Big Bang when the pressure of the quark-gluon gas balanced the binding energy density of the graviton film. Through theoretical analysis, we demonstrate that the graviton film, in conjunction with the quark-gluon gas, is a robust structure and that the graviton film has remained unbroken since its formation.
2. Demonstrating that the quark-gluon gas confined within the graviton film does not leak to the outside. This is equivalent to proving that hadron radiation due to hadronization does not occur.

Regarding the second theme, as previously stated, one needs to consider only $t = 10^{-6}$ seconds after the Big Bang or any time thereafter. The background energy scale corresponding to this period is approximately in the range of 150–200 MeV.

In this work, we assume that the quark-gluon plasma consists of a graviton film and a gas of quarks and gluons, where the graviton film confines the quark-gluon gas, in alignment with the proposal in [3, 1]. When referring to the quark-gluon plasma in this study, we always mean the structure of a quark-gluon gas *together with* the graviton film, not just the quark-gluon gas.

The gravitational potential energy of real graviton pairs in the graviton film has been analyzed at the quantum field-theoretic level in [1]; therefore, this result enables us to evaluate the energy density of the graviton film at the quantum gravitational level.

The formula for the pressure of the quark-gluon gas is known [7, 8]²:

$$p = \frac{\pi^2}{90} \left(2(N_c^2 - 1) + \frac{7}{2}N_cN_f \right) \frac{(k_B T)^4}{(\hbar c)^3}. \quad (1)$$

Here, k_B denotes the Boltzmann constant. This formula depends on the number of colors, N_c , and number of flavors, N_f . We choose $N_c = 3$ and $N_f = 2$ in this study; however, increasing the number of flavors N_f does not significantly affect the comparison between the energy density of the graviton film and the pressure of the quark-gluon gas. Choosing larger values for N_f , up to six, does not influence the core argument of this paper.

We ignore the bag pressure B ³ in this study for two reasons. First, the expected value of B is negligibly small at the energy scale where the quark-gluon gas pressure could potentially balance the energy density of the graviton film. Second, including B only decreases the pressure value, meaning that ignoring B provides an upper bound for the quark-gluon gas pressure. If we establish that the energy density of the graviton film is always greater than this upper bound, it immediately follows that the graviton film energy density is always greater than the actual pressure of the gas. Thus, ignoring B does not affect our conclusion.

We use the Friedmann–Robertson–Walker (FRW) model to evaluate the temperature evolution of the universe since the Big Bang. Gravitons are considered to have emerged approximately 10^{-43} seconds after the Big Bang, and the graviton film would have formed around this time. Whether quarks and gluons existed at this moment or emerged sometime after $t = 10^{-43}$ seconds remains undetermined.

In this study, we deduced that the pressure of the quark-gluon gas could have equaled the energy density of the graviton film only around $t = 10^{-43}$ seconds after the Big Bang. Our result does not depend on whether quarks and gluons existed at that moment. If they did, the pressure of the gas they constituted could have equaled the binding energy density of the graviton film at that time. If they did not yet exist and emerged sometime later, then there was no moment after the Big Bang when the pressure of the quark-gluon gas and the energy density of the graviton film were equal. In this latter scenario, the binding energy density of the graviton film always exceeds the pressure of the quark-gluon gas.

From this computational result, we conclude that from the formation of the graviton film to the present moment, the pressure of the quark-gluon gas has never exceeded the binding energy density of the graviton film. The exact moment in the early universe when quarks and gluons appeared does not affect this conclusion.

²The binding potential energy of real gravitons per pair in the graviton film is at the Planck energy scale [1]. The quark-gluon gas pressure can only match the potential energy density of the graviton film when the background temperature of the universe is extremely high. However, according to asymptotic freedom [9, 10], the strong coupling becomes very small in this regime. Therefore, we do not consider higher-order corrections in powers of the strong coupling, as they are inconsequential in this context and do not affect the physics of the derived conclusions.

³This is a conceptual analogue of the MIT bag constant [11].

We discuss the first theme in Section 2, demonstrating that the pressure of the quark-gluon gas has never exceeded the binding energy density of the graviton film since its formation (or since the appearance of quarks and gluons). This confirms that the graviton film has remained robust since its formation.

Once the background temperature in the universe sufficiently cools, the quark-gluon gas confined within the graviton film could undergo hadronization, emitting hadrons outside the film. The threshold temperature below which hadronization occurs must be about 150–200 MeV, corresponding to the moment $t = 10^{-6}$ seconds after the Big Bang. However, once a hadron is produced near the graviton film, the film's strong gravitational potential attracts the hadron, causing it to fall toward the film. This second theme is discussed in Section 3.

First, we compute the potential generated by the interaction between a real graviton and a hadron. Nonperturbative effects must be incorporated to evaluate the quantum gravitational effect in this interaction, as discussed in Section 3.1. We utilize the computational scheme introduced in [1]. Based on these computational results, we prove in Section 3.2 that a hadron produced outside the graviton film immediately falls toward the film. This argument demonstrates that hadron radiation does not occur and that the quark-gluon gas cannot escape.

We present our concluding remarks in Section 4.

The hypothesis that a virtual graviton with momentum exceeding a threshold value generates a Kerr black hole geometry leads to an ultraviolet-finite, consistent four-dimensional quantum gravitational theory, as shown in [12]. In this study, we adopt this perspective, treating elementary particles as point particles in four-dimensional spacetime. Perturbative analyses of quantum gravity can be found, e.g., in [13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

2 Comparison of the bond of the graviton film and the pressure of the quark-gluon gas confined within it

2.1 Evaluation of the energy density in the graviton film

We compute the energy density of the graviton film, composed of real gravitons bound together. Real gravitons separated by distances on the order of the Planck length l_P are strongly bound owing to the nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect [1]. The energy of the graviton film per unit area, divided by the range of the quantum gravitational force, corresponds to pressure. The energy of the graviton film per unit area, divided by the reach of the quantum gravitational force, on the other hand, is by definition the energy density of the graviton film. Therefore, by comparing the energy density of the graviton film with the pressure of the quark-gluon gas that the graviton film confines, one can determine whether the pressure of the quark-gluon gas can surpass the bond of the graviton film.

The mechanism by which real gravitons, separated by distances on the order of the Planck length, form a film structure was discussed in [1]. The argument given in [1] is, in brief, as follows: owing to the nonperturbative effect of quantum gravity, the virtual graviton propa-

gator transitions to one in a curved spacetime background when the quantum gravitational effect is significant. As a result, a real graviton becomes a composite-like object, acquiring an effective mass $\sqrt{2}m_P$ due to the self-energy correction, where m_P represents the Planck mass, and real gravitons become strongly bound together. This quantum gravitational effect is expected to become apparent at distances on the order of the Planck length l_P ⁴. Due to this nonperturbative effect, real gravitons separated by distances on the order of the Planck length form a film structure.

Through computation at the quantum field-theoretic level, it was derived in [1] that, to leading order, the gravitational potential between two real gravitons separated by distance r is given as follows:

$$V = -\frac{2Gm_P^2}{r}. \quad (2)$$

Since this effect is limited to distances on the order of the Planck length l_P , the absolute value of the potential energy, $|V|$, is on the order of the Planck energy, E_P [1].

We consider the structure of the quark-gluon plasma to be a graviton film confining the quark-gluon gas. Since the size of the quark-gluon plasma produced in the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) experiment is about 10 fermi, the graviton film has a size approximately of the same order. (The size of the graviton film in the quark-gluon plasma in the early universe can be larger than 10 fermi, as the size of the quark-gluon plasma in the early universe could be larger than that produced in the experiment.) In contrast, the spacing of the graviton film is on the order of the Planck length l_P [1]. Thus, the overall size of the graviton film is far larger than the area of the graviton film corresponding to the characteristic length scale. This implies that we can use a flat-geometry approximation when considering the area of the film corresponding to the characteristic length scale⁵.

Given these considerations, we find that one can use l_P as the characteristic range of the quantum gravitational potential generated by a real graviton. Therefore, we divide the potential energy of the graviton per unit area by l_P to obtain the energy density.

We express the spacing of the real gravitons that constitute the graviton film as $c_1 l_P$, where c_1 represents an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ constant. Then, the potential energy of real gravitons per pair is

$$-\frac{2Gm_P^2}{c_1 l_P} = -\frac{2}{c_1} E_P. \quad (3)$$

The configuration in which a real graviton is placed at the center of a circle of radius $c_1 l_P$, with a regular hexagon inscribed in this circle and a real graviton positioned at each of the six vertices of the hexagon, defines the arrangement of real gravitons with spacing $c_1 l_P$ (Figure 1). Using this configuration, we estimate the potential energy of the graviton film per unit area.

⁴The effect of a real graviton becoming a composite-like object and acquiring an effective mass due to the self-energy correction vanishes at distances longer than the Planck-length scale.

⁵The statement that the virtual graviton propagator transitions to one in a curved spacetime refers to the virtual process [1]. This curved spacetime background does not correspond to the curved geometry of the graviton film itself.

Figure 1: The configuration of real gravitons is displayed. Real gravitons are positioned at the six vertices and the center of a regular hexagon. The twelve solid straight lines represent adjacent real graviton pairs, consisting of the six edges of the hexagon along with the six straight lines connecting the center to the vertices. The displayed image corresponds to the configuration of real gravitons with six nearest neighbors. This pattern extends throughout the entire graviton film.

Before proceeding with the computation, we offer a remark on the estimation of c_1 . The number n of nearest neighbors in the aforementioned configuration of real gravitons is six, $n = 6$. According to mean-field analysis [1], the relation $d < \frac{n}{2\sqrt{2}}l_P$ holds between the spacing d of real gravitons and the number of nearest neighbors n . In the situation under discussion, we have

$$d < \frac{6}{2\sqrt{2}}l_P = \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}}l_P, \quad (4)$$

which implies $c_1 \sim \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}} \sim 2.12$.

Now, we compute the energy density in the graviton film. Since there are twelve nearest pairs of real gravitons per area $\pi (c_1 l_P)^2$ in the configuration illustrated in Figure 1 (corresponding to twelve solid straight lines, consisting of six lines connecting the center of the circle to the six vertices of the hexagon and six edges of the hexagon), and each pair carries the gravitational potential energy $-\frac{2}{c_1}E_P$, the total potential energy is twelve times this energy: $-\frac{24}{c_1}E_P$. This is the potential energy carried by the graviton film per area $\pi (c_1 l_P)^2$. Therefore, the potential energy of the graviton film per unit area is

$$-\frac{24E_P}{c_1 \cdot \pi c_1^2 l_P^2} = -\frac{24}{\pi c_1^3} \frac{E_P}{l_P^2}. \quad (5)$$

Finally, dividing this quantity by the characteristic length l_P , we deduce the energy density $\rho_{\text{grav. film}}$ as follows:

$$\rho_{\text{grav. film}} = -\frac{24}{\pi c_1^3} \frac{E_P}{l_P^3}. \quad (6)$$

We compare the absolute value of this quantity with the pressure of the quark-gluon gas in the next section.

2.2 Comparison of the bond of the graviton film and the pressure of the quark-gluon gas since the Big Bang

The pressure of an ideal quark-gluon gas is given by (1). N_c and N_f represent the numbers of colors and flavors, respectively. We choose $N_c = 3$ and $N_f = 2$ in this study. However, as noted in the Introduction, setting higher values for N_f up to six does not alter the core conclusion we deduce. Furthermore, we ignore the bag pressure B for two reasons mentioned in the Introduction. Therefore, under these conditions, the formula for the quark-gluon gas pressure becomes:

$$p_{QG} = \frac{37\pi^2 (k_B T)^4}{90 (\hbar c)^3}. \quad (7)$$

We derive the condition under which this equals the absolute value of the energy density of the graviton film, $|\rho_{\text{grav.film}}|$, (6) as deduced in Section 2.1.

The equality $|\rho_{\text{grav.film}}| = p_{QG}$ can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{24 E_P}{\pi c_1^3 l_P^3} = \frac{37\pi^2 (k_B T)^4}{90 (\hbar c)^3}. \quad (8)$$

Multiplying both sides by $(\hbar c)^3$ and noting the relation $\frac{\hbar c}{l_P} = E_P$, this equality can be rewritten as:

$$E_P^4 = c_1^3 \frac{37\pi^3}{24 \cdot 90} (k_B T)^4. \quad (9)$$

Noting that c_1 is an order $\mathcal{O}(1)$ constant, this equality implies that the quark-gluon gas pressure could equal the potential energy density of the graviton film only when the temperature T is extremely high, such that $k_B T$ is comparable to the Planck energy. Such a high temperature could only be achieved in a very early, radiation-dominated universe.

It is widely known that in a radiation-dominated early universe, the following relation holds between time after the Big Bang, t , and $k_B T$:

$$t = 1.3 \left(\frac{1 \text{ MeV}}{k_B T} \right)^2 \text{ s}. \quad (10)$$

Here, t has dimensions of seconds, and s at the end of the right-hand side represents seconds. Utilizing this relation, condition (9) can be rewritten as

$$E_P^4 = c_1^3 \cdot 1.3^2 \frac{37\pi^3}{24 \cdot 90} t^{-2}. \quad (11)$$

Solving for t , one finds the time (in seconds after the Big Bang) at which the quark-gluon gas equals the potential energy density of the graviton film:

$$t = c_1^{3/2} \cdot 1.3\pi \sqrt{\frac{37\pi}{24 \cdot 90}} \frac{1}{E_P^2}. \quad (12)$$

Noting that $E_P \sim 1.2 \times 10^{22}$ MeV and that c_1 is an order $\mathcal{O}(1)$ constant, the moment at which the pressure of the quark-gluon gas equals the potential energy density of the graviton film falls within the range 10^{-44} s to 10^{-43} s after the Big Bang.

To be precise, it would be more accurate to state that the quark-gluon gas *could have* equaled the potential energy density of the graviton film rather than “*equals*,” since it is undetermined whether quarks and gluons existed yet during this period.

After this period, it becomes impossible for the quark-gluon gas pressure to exceed the bond of the graviton film, as the energy density of the graviton film becomes far greater than the quark-gluon gas pressure—evident since the quark-gluon gas pressure is proportional to the fourth power of the temperature of the universe, T^4 , which decreases as time elapses. $k_B T$ becomes far smaller than the Planck energy scale shortly after the period from 10^{-44} s to 10^{-43} s after the Big Bang.

The period from 10^{-44} s to 10^{-43} s corresponds to the Planck era, and the graviton is expected to emerge around this time. The graviton film should have formed either during or after this period. Therefore, there is no moment at which the confined quark-gluon gas pressure exceeds the bond of the graviton film after the film has formed, meaning that **the graviton film has existed robustly from its formation to the present moment.**

At this point, it is worth pointing out an important aspect. For real gravitons to form a film structure, they need to be positioned within distances on the order of the Planck length. A real graviton acquires an effective mass on the order of the Planck mass owing to the quantum gravitational effect, and this effect becomes apparent only at distances on the order of the Planck length, as pointed out in [1]. Therefore, this effective mass has a physical effect within distances on the order of the Planck length, which means that real gravitons are bound to form a film only when they are within this distance scale. This observation, along with the presence of a graviton film, **strongly suggests that there was a moment when the size of the universe was comparable to the Planck length scale.** If the size of the universe has been much larger than this scale ever since it arose, then a situation where real gravitons are located within distances on the order of the Planck length is unlikely. The presence of a real graviton film surrounding every atomic nucleus implies that a large number of graviton films exist in the universe. The fact that there was a moment when the size of the universe was comparable to the Planck length scale explains the existence of such a number of graviton films. Therefore, **the presence of a real graviton film surrounding every atomic nucleus, as proposed in [1], supports the Big Bang theory,** at least partially, in this theoretical sense.

3 Demonstration that the quark-gluon gas is confined within a graviton film

3.1 Computational method using Feynman diagrams

We showed in Section 2 that the graviton film does not break due to the quark-gluon gas it confines, since its formation in the early universe. When a portion of the gas attempts to escape from the film—because the quark-gluon gas inside the film is in a high-energy state, whereas outside the film it is in a low-energy state—there must be a quantum chromodynamics (QCD) phase transition at the film, as it serves as the boundary.

Since quarks, antiquarks, and gluons in the gas interact through the strong force, when a portion of the gas attempts to escape, it transitions to a low-energy state. The QCD coupling becomes extremely strong, pulling it back into the rest of the gas, preventing its escape.

Given this observation, for the quark-gluon gas to escape outside the film, the entire gas must escape, breaking the bond of the graviton film. As we showed in Section 2.2, this is impossible, and it does not occur.

The only remaining possibility for a portion of the quark-gluon gas to escape outside the graviton film is hadronization. As noted in the Introduction, for hadronization to occur, the temperature of the universe and the quark-gluon plasma must be low enough, corresponding to $k_B T$ in the range of 150–200 MeV or lower. Thus, for $k_B T$ values higher than this range, the discussion in Section 2 suffices to show that the quark-gluon gas does not escape the graviton film.

If hadronization occurs, the quark-gluon plasma would produce a hadron outside but very close to the graviton film, emitting it outward. This could result in hadronic radiation. However, real gravitons in the graviton film have effective mass [1]. As a result, the graviton film generates an attractive gravitational potential that acts on the produced hadron, pulling it back toward the film. As we discussed earlier, hadronization occurs only when $k_B T$ is in the range of 150–200 MeV or below. In this case, a standard argument shows that the energy of the produced hadron would be in the range of a few hundred MeV to a few GeV.

As we will show in Section 3.2, the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the produced hadron has a lower bound that is much higher than the hadron’s energy range. This means that the produced hadron will immediately fall back toward the film, and hadronic radiation does not occur.

In this section, as a preliminary step, we demonstrate that a real graviton with an effective mass generates a gravitational potential that acts on a hadron at the quantum field-theoretic level, using Feynman diagrams.

For computational simplicity, we assume that a produced hadron has spin 0 and proceed. The spin of hadrons is not limited to 0; however, in evaluating the gravitational potential energy to leading order by computing the scattering amplitude of a real graviton with effective mass and a hadron, we take a nonrelativistic, stationary limit, where both the real graviton and the hadron are at rest. Therefore, the hadron’s spin does not essentially affect the outcome of the computation. This assumption does not influence the essence of the physics underlying

Figure 2: The displayed leaf Feynman diagram represents the scattering of a real graviton with an effective mass that incorporates the nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect and a hadron. The external lines on the left correspond to the incoming and outgoing states of the real graviton, while the external lines on the right correspond to the incoming and outgoing states of the hadron. The nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect is incorporated into the virtual graviton propagator.

the deduced conclusion.

We follow the computational scheme introduced in [1] to compute the gravitational interaction of a real graviton and a spin-0 hadron, incorporating the nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect to evaluate the gravitational potential between them. The notion of the “leaf Feynman diagram,” incorporating the nonperturbative effects of quantum gravity, was introduced in [1]. As a result, the virtual graviton propagator transitions to one in a curved spacetime background, replacing the flat Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ with a curved spacetime metric $g_{\mu\nu}$. A real graviton behaves like a composite object and acquires an effective mass of $\sqrt{2}m_P$ due to self-energy corrections.

Now, we compute the scattering amplitude of a real graviton and a hadron. We use the $(+, -, -, -)$ convention for the spacetime metric in the computation below. We denote the incoming and outgoing momenta of a real graviton by k_1 and k'_1 , respectively, and the incoming and outgoing momenta of a hadron by k_2 and k'_2 , respectively. For notational brevity, we denote the effective mass of a real graviton, $\sqrt{2}m_P$, by m , i.e., $m := \sqrt{2}m_P$. The rest mass of a hadron is denoted as m_h . q represents the transferred momentum through the virtual graviton propagator. We assign the labels a and b to the incoming state of the real graviton and c and d to the outgoing state of the real graviton. μ, ν are assigned to label the virtual graviton propagator on the real graviton side, whereas ρ, σ are assigned on the hadron side. The corresponding leaf Feynman diagram is illustrated in Figure 2.

In the stationary limit ($q \sim 0$), the three-graviton vertex is given by $\frac{i\kappa}{2} (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) Q_{ab,cd}$ [1], where $Q_{ab,cd} := \frac{1}{2} (\eta_{ac}\eta_{bd} + \eta_{ad}\eta_{bc} - \eta_{ab}\eta_{cd})$, and $\kappa := \sqrt{32\pi G}$. The scalar-scalar-graviton vertex without nonperturbative effects is given by [17] $\frac{i\kappa}{2} (k_{2\rho} k'_{2\sigma} + k'_{2\rho} k_{2\sigma} - \eta_{\rho\sigma} (k_2 \cdot k'_2 - m_h^2))$.

Following the discussion in [1], incorporating the nonperturbative quantum gravitational effect, this is replaced with $\frac{i\kappa}{2} \left(k_{2\rho} k'_{2\sigma} + k'_{2\rho} k_{2\sigma} - g_{\rho\sigma} (k_2 \cdot k'_2 - m_h^2) \right)$. However, in the aforementioned stationary limit, the third term vanishes, simplifying this to $\frac{i\kappa}{2} \left(k_{2\rho} k'_{2\sigma} + k'_{2\rho} k_{2\sigma} \right)$.

Computing analogously to the method given in [1], in the stationary limit ($q \sim 0$), we obtain:

$$i\mathcal{M} = \left(\frac{i\kappa}{2} \right)^2 (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) \frac{i}{2q^2} (g_{\mu\rho} g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma} g_{\nu\rho} - g_{\mu\nu} g_{\rho\sigma}) \times (k_2^\rho k_2'^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2^\sigma) Q_{ab,cd}. \quad (13)$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) (g_{\mu\rho} g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma} g_{\nu\rho}) (k_2^\rho k_2'^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2^\sigma) \\ &= 2(2(k_1 \cdot k_2)(k_1 \cdot k'_2) + 2(k'_1 \cdot k_2)(k'_1 \cdot k'_2)) \\ &= 4(k_1 \cdot k_2)(k_1 \cdot k'_2) + 4(k'_1 \cdot k_2)(k'_1 \cdot k'_2), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) g_{\mu\nu} g_{\rho\sigma} (k_2^\rho k_2'^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2^\sigma) \\ &= (k_1^2 + k_1'^2) 2k_2 \cdot k'_2 \\ &= 4m^2 k_2 \cdot k'_2, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where we used $k_1^2 = k_1'^2 = m^2$. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (k_1^\mu k_1^\nu + k_1'^\mu k_1'^\nu) (g_{\mu\rho} g_{\nu\sigma} + g_{\mu\sigma} g_{\nu\rho} - g_{\mu\nu} g_{\rho\sigma}) (k_2^\rho k_2'^\sigma + k_2'^\rho k_2^\sigma) \\ &= 4(k_1 \cdot k_2)(k_1 \cdot k'_2) + 4(k'_1 \cdot k_2)(k'_1 \cdot k'_2) - 4m^2 k_2 \cdot k'_2. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

However, in the stationary limit, where both the real graviton and the hadron are at rest with $q \sim 0$, this simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} & 4(m \cdot m_h)^2 + 4(m \cdot m_h)^2 - 4m^2 \cdot m_h^2 \\ &= 4(m \cdot m_h)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Thus, one finds

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M} &= -\frac{32\pi G}{8q^2} 4(m \cdot m_h)^2 \\ &= \frac{4\pi G m \cdot m_h}{|\mathbf{q}|^2} 2m \cdot 2m_h. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

After applying the Fourier transform and multiplying by $\frac{1}{2m \cdot 2m_h}$ for normalization, we deduce the gravitational potential energy between the real graviton with effective mass and the hadron:

$$\boxed{V = -G \frac{m \cdot m_h}{r} = -\sqrt{2}G \frac{m_P \cdot m_h}{r}}, \quad (19)$$

where r represents the distance between the real graviton and the hadron.

We will use this result to demonstrate that hadron radiation from the quark-gluon plasma does not occur in the next section.

3.2 Completing the proof: hadron emission from the graviton film does not occur

As we noted previously, the only remaining possibility for the quark-gluon gas confined in the quark-gluon plasma is to leak outside the film through hadron radiation via hadronization. We also stated that for hadronization to occur, the background temperature of the universe must be sufficiently low, in the range of 150–200 MeV or below.

The energy range of the hadron depends on the rest mass of the emitted hadron. The energy of the emitted hadron must be comparable to its rest mass: for lighter hadrons, the energy is in the range of hundreds of MeV, while for heavier hadrons, the energy can reach up to a few GeV.

Now, using the computational result we deduced in Section 3.1, we demonstrate that the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the emitted hadron is much higher than the aforementioned energy range of the hadron.

We consider the model of real gravitons with $n = 6$ nearest neighbors, as discussed in Section 2.1. As noted there, the local geometry on the order of the Planck length is small enough compared to the entire graviton film that the flat-geometry approximation applies.

If hadronization were to occur, the produced hadron outside the film would be very close to the film—since the spacing of real gravitons composing the film is on the order of the Planck length—at a distance comparable to the Planck length. Therefore, we may assume that the produced hadron is positioned at a point along the vertical axis, perpendicular to the plane in which real gravitons lie, at a distance l_P from the nearest real graviton. We label the real graviton closest to the hadron as O , and the configuration of local real gravitons is illustrated in Figure 3. We denote the spacing of real gravitons by $d = c_1 l_P$, as in Section 2.1, and as we remarked there, relation (4) holds for the spacing, thus c_1 has an upper bound: $c_1 < \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}}$.

In the first layer, six real gravitons are positioned at the vertices of a regular hexagon centered at O , with the length of an edge equal to $c_1 l_P$. They are separated by a distance $c_1 l_P$ from the real graviton O . In the second layer, six regular hexagons surround the hexagon containing O , with six real gravitons at their centers, each at a distance of $\sqrt{3}c_1 l_P$ from O , and eighteen real gravitons along the outer perimeter of the second layer, twelve of which are at a distance of $\sqrt{7}c_1 l_P$ from O and six at a distance of $2c_1 l_P$ from O . The third layer consists

Figure 3: A local geometry of the graviton film with $n = 6$ nearest neighbors. The flat-geometry approximation is applied. A real graviton, labeled O , is located at the center of a hexagon, which itself is positioned at the center of this image. Real gravitons are positioned at the centers and vertices of the hexagons. Six hexagons surround the hexagon containing the real graviton O , forming the second layer. The third layer consists of twelve hexagons surrounding the six hexagons from the previous layer.

of twelve regular hexagons surrounding the six hexagons from the previous layer, with twelve real gravitons at their centers—six at a distance of $\sqrt{12}c_1l_P$ from O and six at a distance of $3c_1l_P$ from O . Additionally, there are thirty real gravitons along the outer perimeter: twelve at a distance of $\sqrt{19}c_1l_P$ from O , twelve at a distance of $\sqrt{13}c_1l_P$ from O , and six at a distance of $4c_1l_P$ from O .

This structure extends repetitively; however, we stop here and evaluate a lower bound for the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the hadron, as the effective mass acquired by real gravitons is expected to have physical significance only within distances on the order of the Planck length.

We denote the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the hadron by V . From the argument we gave previously and using (19), the absolute value $|V|$ has the following lower bound:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |V| > & \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{3c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{7c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{4c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{12c_1^2 + 1}} \right. & (20) \\
 & \left. + \frac{6}{\sqrt{9c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{19c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{13c_1^2 + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{16c_1^2 + 1}} \right) \sqrt{2} \frac{Gm_P \cdot m_h}{l_P}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Noting that $c_1^2 < \frac{9}{2}$ and $\frac{Gm_P}{l_P} = c^2$, this quantity also has the lower bound:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{\frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{3 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{7 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{4 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{12 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{6}{\sqrt{9 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{19 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{12}{\sqrt{13 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} + \frac{6}{\sqrt{16 \times \frac{9}{2} + 1}} \right) \sqrt{2} m_h c^2 \\ & \sim 19.663 m_h c^2. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, we find that

$$|V| > 19.663 m_h c^2. \quad (22)$$

This pull of the gravitational potential energy is much higher than the energy range of the hadron (if produced outside the graviton film). For example, when the hadron is a pion, the rest mass is about $m_h = 135 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, and in this case, $|V| > 2654 \text{ MeV}$, which is much higher than the energy range of hundreds of MeV. When the hadron is a proton, the rest mass is about $m_h = 938 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, and we have $|V| > 18.4 \text{ GeV}$, which is much higher than the energy range of a few GeV.

We remark on the deduced lower bound of the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the hadron. We set a cutoff, including only real gravitons contained in the first three layers of regular hexagons to deduce this lower bound; thus, this is a stringent lower bound for the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy. However, real gravitons in additional n th layers ($n \geq 4$) can contribute to the gravitational potential energy, implying that the inclusion of such additional layers could yield an even higher lower bound.

The stringent lower bound of the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy between the graviton film and the hadron that we just derived **completely rules out the possibility of a hadron escaping from the graviton film via hadron radiation**. Since the derived lower bound shows that the absolute value of the gravitational potential energy is much higher than the energy range of the hadron, **its falling back into the graviton film owing to the gravitational pull of the film once it is produced outside the film is decisive**. This completes the proof that the quark-gluon gas cannot escape from the graviton film. The quark-gluon gas remains confined within the graviton film in the quark-gluon plasma.

4 Concluding remarks

The graviton film consists of real gravitons that acquire an effective mass on the order of the Planck mass owing to the nonperturbative effect of quantum gravity. As a result of this effect, real gravitons are bound together to form this aggregated body. The reach of this effective mass is expected to be on the order of the Planck length. The spacing of real gravitons in the

film is therefore on the order of the Planck length, and the potential energy per pair is at the Planck energy scale. Consequently, the energy density of the graviton film is on the order of c^2 times the Planck density ρ_P , $c^2\rho_P$.

For the pressure of the quark-gluon gas confined within the graviton film to equal the energy density of the graviton film, an extremely high background temperature in the early universe is required. This value can be achieved only in the range of 10^{-44} s to 10^{-43} s after the Big Bang. This means that the quark-gluon gas pressure has never exceeded the binding force of real gravitons in the graviton film since its formation.

Furthermore, for the graviton film to have formed at some point in the early universe, the size of the universe must have been comparable to the Planck length at the time of formation. This strongly suggests the possibility that the universe was once comparable in size to the Planck length scale in the early universe. This observation seems to support, at least partially, the Big Bang theory.

We also demonstrated that, owing to the gravitational potential generated by the graviton film, hadrons produced via hadronization outside the film immediately fall toward the film. This completely rules out the possibility that the confined quark-gluon gas could leak outside the film through hadron radiation. Therefore, we provided a rigorous proof that the confined quark-gluon gas cannot escape the graviton film.

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